

The Liminal Landscape of Northern Ireland in the 1970s: The In-betweenness, Permanent Liminality and Communitas in *Milkman*

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Abstract

Milkman, the winner of the 2018 Booker Prize, displays the repressive nature of people's lives in Northern Ireland during the Troubles in the 1970s through the sexual harassment suffered by the protagonist. This paper will use “in-betweenness,” “permanent liminality” and “communitas” as keywords to analyze the liminality of Northern Ireland in the 1970s. Based on the analysis of in-betweenness and permanent liminality, and inspired by O'Brennan (2023), this paper points out that Northern Ireland in the 1970s was a liminal space. As the kernel of society and the key to survival, liminality is the condition of in-betweenness. Fortunately, what is conciliative is that communitas is formed in the course of liminality, through which people help each other and work together to survive and fight back in a dark society. This paper gives a relationship model of the keywords, stressing that although communitas is the smallest part, it is a supporting force. The analysis of the paper not only fills in the lack of liminal research in the existing studies of *Milkman*, but also provides a historical reference for Northern Ireland, which is still in liminality today.

Keywords: *Milkman*, liminality, permanent liminality, in-betweenness, communitas.

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Introduction

Milkman, written by Northern Irish author Anna Burns, has won the 2018 Booker Prize. It revolves around middle sister, an 18-year-old girl who is stalked and harassed by a high-ranking member of a military organization nicknamed Milkman. The paper will go as follows: First, this paper will use the theories of Gayatri Chakravorty Spivak and Arpad Szakolczai, adopting “in-betweenness” and “permanent liminality” as keywords to analyze the middle state of the characters in *Milkman* and how some people strive to break in-betweenness. Furthermore, the paper will utilize the conclusion presented by O'Brennan (2023): “Liminality as a condition of ‘in-betweenness’” (p. 135), arguing for this idea by claiming that Northern Ireland in the Troubles was also a liminal territory. Next, the paper will utilize the theory of Victor Turner, taking “communitas” as a keyword to dig into the feminist agency and resistance in *Milkman*. A relationship model for the keywords will be formed in order to present the logic of the paper more explicitly.

Literature Review

As Burns's most internationally acclaimed novel, *Milkman* has been examined at length by academics, with studies going from multiple perspectives: Dystopia, power, violence, space, type, feminism, and gossip. Callan (2023) viewed *Milkman* “an innovative dystopia” (p. 513),ⁱ Morales-Ladrón (2023)

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examined “the postpanopticon society of *Milkman*” (p. 10)ⁱⁱ from the angle of power, and Darling (2021) discussed the linguistic and epistemic violence in *Milkman*.ⁱⁱⁱ Mathuria (2022) probed into space in *Milkman*, proposing that instead of using a clear sectarian interpretation of space, middle sister creates a categorization system that highlights her logic to space (p. 187).^{iv} Moreover, two scholars analyzed the type of *Milkman*, having a controversy about whether *Milkman* belongs to bildungsroman or picaresque work (Hutton 2019; Malone 2022).^v Regarding feminism, *Milkman* has been carefully studied through the lens of female phenomenology (Routray and Gaur, 2024),^{vi} feminist poststructuralism (Hossain, 2023),^{vii} and Marxist feminism (Maqbool et al. 2022)^{viii}. Last, Wall (2023) examined the gossip, summarizing that “gossip constitutes a kind of verbal labour and feminine guerrilla intelligence in the novel” (p. 69).

The above researches and studies compose sound foundation for the present paper. However, few scholars have done a systematic study of in-betweenness or liminality in *Milkman*. This paper, through the theories of Spivak, Szokolczai, and Turner, will fill this research gap by making a detailed textual analysis of people’s in-betweenness and liminality. Heidemann (2016) explored the negative liminality of Northern Ireland after the Good Friday Agreement, through which the author “helps diagnose the political predicaments of post-Agreement Northern Ireland at large” (p. 17). O’ Brennan (2023) studied Northern Ireland as a liminal space after Brexit, and pointed out that “Northern Ireland might thus be thought of as a place where people seek a sense of place within a ‘non-place’, where everyone is an insider and outsider simultaneously” (p. 136). Therefore, the state of present-day Northern Ireland has been well studied by scholars, while few scholars have analyzed the liminality of Northern Ireland in the Troubles. Enlightened by O’ Brennan (2023), this paper argues that Northern Ireland in the 1970s was also a liminal space, with liminality as the essence that brings about manifestations of in-betweenness. By showing the violence, oppression and how individuals survive in a complicated political and social context, the historical memory and social trauma of Northern Ireland can be seen, which has implications for Northern Ireland to learn the lessons of history and get out of the present-day state of liminality.

Theoretical Foundation and Social Context

Spivak used Jacques Derrida’s class stratification in India in “Can the Subaltern Speak.” Derrida divided India’s classes into four: “dominant foreign groups; dominant indigenous groups on the all-India level; dominant indigenous groups at the regional and local levels, and ‘people’ and ‘subaltern classes”” (Spivak, 1988, p. 284). Spivak (1988) defined the third class as follows: “The third group on the list, the buffer group, as it were, between the people and the great macrostructural dominant groups, is itself defined as a place of in-betweenness” (p. 284). Spivak utilized Guha’s point of view: “The same class or element which was dominant in one area...could be among the dominated in another. This could and did create many ambiguities and contradictions in attitudes and alliances, especially among... to the category of people or subaltern classes” (Guha, 1982, as cited in Spivak, 1988, p. 284). Thus, through “place of in-betweenness” (Spivak, 1988, p. 284), Spivak discussed the heterogeneity of subalterns. The subaltern group is not a single, homogenized group, but comprises individuals with different backgrounds, experiences, and positions. Through the keyword “in-betweenness,” this paper will not only show the intermediate state of the residents, but also the heterogeneity of subalterns by analyzing the roles in *Milkman*, especially the fierce contradiction between middle sister and ma.

A word with similar meaning to “in-betweenness” is “liminality,” with “liminality” having a broader and deeper meaning. The word “liminal” is derived from the Latin word “limen,” which is translated to “threshold.” The term “first appeared in publication in the field of psychology in 1884, but the idea was introduced to the field of anthropology in 1909 by Arnold van Gennep” (Chakraborty, 2016, p. 146). In his work *The Rites of Passage*, Gennep (1960) divided “rites of passage” into three steps: “preliminal rites (rites of separation), liminal rites (rites of transition), and postliminal rites (rites of incorporation)” (p. 11). After Gennep, anthropologist Victor Turner further expanded the use of liminality. He observed the ambiguity of liminality: “The attributes of liminality or of liminal personae (‘threshold people’) are necessarily ambiguous, since this condition and these persons elude or slip through the network of classifications that normally locate states and positions in cultural space” (Turner, 1991, p. 95).

Furthermore, he illustrated the concept of “communitas” and pointed out that “in closed or structured societies, it is the marginal or ‘inferior’ person or the ‘outsider’... which in its turn relates to the model we have termed ‘communitas’” (Turner, 1991, p. 186). According to Hambrick (1979), “communitas is Turner’s name for the distinctive type of community that emerges in the liminal period and is a relatively unstructured and undifferentiated communion or fellowship” (p. 540). A scholar concluded the center idea of communitas, which is “the comradeship and fellowship of people in the midst of liminal ritual” (Turner, 2008, p. 36). It connotes to “the sense of sharing and intimacy that develops among persons who experience liminality as a group” (Turner, 2008, p. 36). Moreover, Turner relates communitas to structure and anti-structure, “equates anti-structure with communitas and hence sees it as presenting the possibility of freedom, spontaneity and creativity and finally as a condition necessary to the continued health of the social order itself” (Hambrick, 1979, p. 540). Based on Turner’s explanation, communitas can be categorized into three types: “(1) existential or spontaneous, (2) normative, and (3) ideological. The first is a truly structureless ‘happening’... prior to any necessity of social organization. This is the form that might be referred to as the ‘typical’ manifestation of communitas” (Hambrick, 1979, p. 540), and this is the type this paper will mainly discuss. Later, “Homi Bhabha theorizes the Third Space of confusion and paradox, or liminality, within the context of (post) colonialism” (Kalua, 2009, p. 25). The concepts of “third space,” “mimicry” and “hybridity” proposed by Bhabha has become valuable terms in today’s postcolonial study.

Besides, based on the theory of Victor Turner, Szokolczai (2020) introduced the concept of “permanent liminality” and pointed out its paradox, since liminality is described as a transient condition. Turner emphasized that the expression of liminal “state” is not correct as the word “state” implies fixity, which is not the feature of liminality (p. 211). Nevertheless, he also observed that “with the increasing specialization of society and culture... what was in tribal society principally a set of transitional qualities ‘betwixt and between’ defined states of culture and society has become itself an institutionalized state” (Turner, 1991, p. 107). Grounded in this idea of Turner, “permanent liminality” appears in Szokolczai’s book *Reflexive historical sociology*. Murphy and McDowell (2019) also summarized Turner’s hints: “Certain environments can lead to an ‘institutionalisation of liminality’ has led to an additional body of work suggesting that liminality can gradually become a permanent state” (p. 2501). In other words, some special social or cultural conditions can always keep people in liminality, thus leading them to the state of permanent liminality.

Set in Ardoyne, a Catholic community in Belfast, the social context of *Milkman* is Northern Ireland in the 1970s, when it belongs to the Troubles. During this period, Northern Ireland was deeply torn apart by religion and politics. The majority of its residents are Protestants, who tend to favor remaining in the UK, while Catholics seek unification with the Republic of Ireland. This division has led to prolonged violent conflicts, particularly during the Troubles from the late 1960s to the 1990s, which witnessed the activities of organizations like the Irish Republican Army (IRA). In the three decades, society was in an extremely volatile state: Bombs, riots, and armies were a regular part of people’s lives, and death was something that people had to deal with on a regular basis. Moreover, in *Milkman*, middle sister’s narration “is a vivid demonstration of how a community engaged in sectarian conflict is not merely traumatized by the extraordinary exposure to violence; the way the community responds to that trauma becomes another form of violence inflicted upon its members” (Farrell, 2020, p. 817). Therefore, DenHoed (2020) discussed the suicide in Northern Ireland: It “has one of the highest suicide rates in the world—a trend that researchers attribute to widespread PTSD from the troubles” (p. 12). This shows the psychological trauma caused by the social chaos of the Troubles. This chaotic social context is also fundamental in the analysis in this paper.

An Analysis of In-betweenness in *Milkman*

In this section, the paper will specifically analyze what kind of in-between behaviors the characters adopt, in order to show how the roles are imprisoned in in-betweenness. Not only that, where there is injustice

there must also be resistance. So, the paper will also probe into the act of breaking in-betweenness in *Milkman*, thus revealing the localized resistance of the community residents.

In-betweenness is a Way to Live: The Omnipresent Performance of In-betweenness

The Ardoyne community middle sister lives in is governed by an anti-British government military organization, with IRA occupying high probability. As the protagonist, middle sister performs in-betweenness in her political state. In the face of the conflict between Protestants and Catholics, middle sister does not support either side. For the issue of “over the water” (euphemism that indicates England), “over the road” (euphemism that indicates community which has a different political stance with Ardoyne), “this of course was all part of the political problems here which I, for one, didn’t like to get into” (Burns, 2018, p. 28). Additionally, “the novel’s characters, too, are designated locatively and existentially, rather than according to proper names” (Sheils, 2024, p. 94). Concerning Burns’s nomenclature, why the narrator of the novel is called middle sister? Her second and fourth brothers are against the local military organization, as is her second brother-in-law. Her second sister has married her second brother-in-law and they live in a country “over the water.” Consequently, these four family members of middle sister are despised by the locals. On the contrary, her little sisters have “wonderful curiosity and guts and passion and engagement. A natural sense too, they have, of entitlement which as you know in this place is rare” (Burns, 2018, pp. 125-126). But the positive qualities of the younger sisters may be gradually erased by this gloomy society. “More often it’s the case that keenness and initiative get stifled here, turned to discouragement, twisted too, into darker channels” (Burns, 2018, p. 126). Therefore, excluding the age factor, Burns may also wish to convey the in-betweenness of political positions and state of living by naming the main character as middle sister. She reads books as she walks, dislikes contemporary literature and prefers only 19th century or earlier literature, all representing her escape from real life. Moreover, the ambiguous narrative strategy Burns adopted in *Milkman*, such as referring England as “over the water,” lets readers feel again the state of intermediation of middle sister: In one aspect, “she is enmeshed in the culture, a product of it and its linguistic particularities, which lends her some authority to explain it” (White, 2021, p. 121). However, in another respect, “she is singular in that culture, with idiosyncratic speech and habits, and therefore somewhat of an outsider within. She narrates, therefore, as a knowing representative of her world and as an individual still trying to understand it” (White, 2021, p. 121). This ambiguous nomenclature may cause some reading difficulties, but it also demonstrates the in-between state of middle sister.

Unfortunately, a man named Milkman, who is most likely a high-ranking member of the IRA organization, sets his sights on middle sister and continues to harass her. Because of his special identity, middle sister is inevitably caught up in the political struggle, and even photographed by the military forces. As the thing spreads, the community is abuzz with rumors, with many believing that middle sister is Milkman’s lover. Even ma, middle sister’s mother, who urges middle sister to get married and does not want the son-in-law to be a military member, also believed these rumors.

The community follows the “victim blaming.” If someone is victimized for doing something, the community only questions the victim and criticizes what the victim has done. Therefore, middle sister cannot clear up the rumors. “Apart from the gossip—and even if there’d been no gossip—my belief from the outset was that not really would I have been heard or believed” (Burns, 2018, pp. 154-155). Haekel (2023) commented that “the border between truth and lies, is created by language” (p. 78), and rumors from community members have already established the border and distorted the facts. Thus, silence is middle sister’s weapon to establish her own border and protect herself. Once she confesses to ma: “So I’d kept silent...I’d asked no questions, answered no questions, gave no confirmation, no refutation. That way, I said, I’d hoped to maintain a border to keep my mind separate...” (Burns, 2018, p. 50). Alder (2024) explained middle sister’s way of thinking: “Speech is a way of admitting shame. To exculpate oneself verbally implies guilt” (p. 142). Nevertheless, gossips make it increasingly difficult for middle sister to define herself. Many people treat her differently because of her relationship with Milkman, and she is even seen as a member of the “groupies,” the titles of women who climb up to powerful men. Although silence is a form of self-protection, it reinforces the misconceptions that others

have about her. Milkman's "assertion of power and the community's mistaken certainty about the affair undermine her agency and credibility" (White, 2021, p. 118). Middle sister has been between rumor and truth ever since, unable to prove herself. This in-betweenness brings great psychological pressure on middle sister, and her body starts experiencing physiological reactions of fear.

Not only middle sister, but residents in Ardoyne community adopt various in-betweenness in their life. People don't get to be themselves as they please in the midst of social upheaval:

So shiny was bad, and 'too sad' was bad, and 'too joyous' was bad, which meant you had to go around not being anything; also not thinking, least not at top level, which was why everybody kept their private thoughts safe and sound in those recesses underneath. (Burns, 2018, p. 50)

This passage represents the in-betweenness of people's everyday state. The only way to maximize one's relatively peaceful life in the turbulent days filled with constant military scrutiny and suspicion is to show in-betweenness. As Crummy (2023) commented: "You could be not womanly enough or too womanly... You could be too smart or too stupid... Most people could never quite see the line before they crossed over to what middle sister describes as 'beyond'". It is the safest to be intermediate, and thus unobtrusive.

Therefore, people seek in-betweenness in marriage. One can't love his/her partner not at all, but one can't love his/her partner too much either. The "wrong-spouse situation" (Burns, 2018, p. 282) is prevalent because people fear to lose the true love in their life. "One was the political situation here in which the spouse you really wanted might not have a premature, violent death, but then again, he or she might have" (Burns, 2018, p. 215). To avoid losing in a volatile society, people choose in-betweenness in marriage, spending lifetime with the "wrong" person. A typical example of this is ma, whose true love is "the man who didn't love anybody" (Burns, 2018, p. 213), a milkman. After Milkman who stalks middle sister shows up, he is called "real milkman" (Burns, 2018, p. 213) to differentiate. But ma ends up marrying da (middle sister's father), who had depression because of the darkness of society and who has passed away. Middle sister herself has also held in-betweenness in her relationship with her maybe-boyfriend, not progressing to a formal relationship. For the couple, Farsi and Hallaji (2022) commented that "the word 'maybe' reflects her mental uncertainty about the roles they both have as the involved parties" (p. 48). Although middle sister sometimes has the desire to break this in-betweenness, she never conducts it. "Great and sustained happiness was far too much to ask of it. That was why marrying in doubt, marrying in guilt, marrying in regret... also in terrible self-sacrifice was pretty much the unspoken matrimonial requisite here" (Burns, 2018, p. 215). The in-betweenness in romantic relationships is also an act of self-protection.

People even have in-betweenness in law. After Milkman's death, McSomebody tries to hurt middle sister in the restroom, but fails due to the presence of "groupies." "The coterie sitting in judgment" was going to charge McSomebody with "quarter-rape charge," but eventually dropped the charge because no one cared about it (Burns, 2018, p. 261). But, as what third brother-in-law is concerned, "rape was rape. It was also black eyes. It was guns in breasts. Hands, fists, weapons, feet, used by male people, deliberately or accidentally-on-purpose against female people" (Burns, 2018, p. 289). Rape should not be divided into fractions.

All these representations of in-betweenness display that it is a way to live. Moreover, the opposition between middle sister and ma in in-betweenness reflects the individual complexity and the subaltern's heterogeneity. Ma adopts in-betweenness in the hope that middle sister can find a stable man to get married, while middle sister's in-betweenness is to maintain her maybe-relationship and not get married. However, staying unmarried is seen by the community as odd, essentially breaking in-betweenness. This is the reason why ma consistently urges middle sister to enter the matrimony. In addition, "the mother's insistence upon her daughter's marriage reflects her adherence to the traditional categories in which a prototypical girl is positioned safely only when she is married properly" (Farsi and Hallaji, 2022, p. 50). Ma, as a middle-aged woman who has suffered a lot from social unrest, has had her temper smoothed out long ago. In a conflict between ma and middle sister, ma expresses her indignation for her daughter's

arrogance: “Is it that you think I haven’t lived, daughter? Is it that you think I haven’t intelligence, haven’t learned anything in all the years I’ve been here” (Burns, 2018, p. 49). As two representatives of in-betweenness, different ages, experiences and personalities cause the two to have different perspectives. And both of them certainly have different experiences and practices from the rest of the subalterns. This is the heterogeneity within the community. Outside the community, whereas Northern Ireland is so culturally and politically different compared to India, the experiences of the subalterns are unlikely to be the same. Thus, through the keyword “in-betweenness,” the manifestations of people’s conformity to a turbulent society and the heterogeneity of the subalterns are well presented.

Boundary Crossing is a Way to Fight: Breaking the Imprisonment of In-betweenness

Based on the analysis above, showing in-betweenness in life is necessary to survive the Troubles. In *Milkman*, the parents of maybe-boyfriend are a successful case. His parents are only obsessed with dancing and show in-betweenness on political issues by having ambiguity between England and Northern Ireland after leaving Ardoyne: “...to the international kudos of stardom they were attaching to their country—though which country, ‘over the border’ or ‘over the water’, was tactfully never referred to (Burns, 2018, p. 38). By adopting in-betweenness, they skillfully shun political trouble and successfully gain reputation worldwide for their glamorous dancing. Thus, it can be said that in-betweenness, as an intermediary state, is a strategy and technique that helps people save a lot of unnecessary trouble.

Nevertheless, it is definitely not the situation where everyone is obedient to the social rules of in-betweenness, and there are those in *Milkman* who want to break the liminal state, the first of which is the real milkman who dares to resist. Alder (2024) also pointed out that the real milkman “offers an interesting example of resistance to these conformist forces” (p. 138). Upon discovering that the local military organization has buried weapons in his house, he throws them all out and does not choose to suffer in silence. For the local military organization, “he voiced dissent over their local rules and regulations...he objected to their courts of nuisance and to the rough justice meted out by them...he made a fuss over the disappearance of suspected informers...” (Burns, 2018, p. 121). He also helps people in the community, even though he does not have a good reputation with the residents. By expressing direct rejection and defiance to the military organization, the real milkman breaks the liminal state of timid and silent tolerance. The second representative is the issue women, who establish a feminist group in Ardoyne community. They want to improve the status of women, but the group “were firmly placed in the category of those way, way beyond-the-pale. The word ‘feminist’ was beyond-the-pale” (Burns, 2018, p. 130). They are the outliers in the community, and they go beyond in-betweenness and courageously break the social norms to make a feminist resistance.

The third representative is the teacher who makes the students look at the sky in French class. Students have “rules of consciousness regarding the likes of color” (Burns, 2018, p. 64), insisting that the sky is only blue. However, the French teacher is relentless and expects students to see and recognize the magnificent colors of the sky at sunset. The scene of the colorful sunset is also on the cover page of *Milkman*. “This focus on the non-linguistic perception of the world—on vision and ultimately aesthetics—does not only provide a different perspective, it also creates the space for truth beyond language, rumours, lies, and mental borders” (Haekel, 2023, p. 80). Pitifully, though the students know the diversified colors in the sky, they will never verbally acknowledge that the sky is any color other than blue. Because

it was the convention not to admit it, not to accept detail for this type of detail would mean choice and choice would mean responsibility and what if we failed in our responsibility? Failed too, in the interrogation of the consequence of seeing more than we could cope with? Worse, what if it was nice, whatever it was, and we liked it, got used to it, were cheered up by it, came to rely upon it, only for it to go away, or be wrenched away, never to come back again? Better not to have had it in the first place was the prevailing feeling, and that was why blue was the colour for our sky to be. (Burns, 2018, p. 63)

This is similar to “marrying the wrong spouse.” Because one does not want to take responsibility and suffer the pain of loss, it is best not to have it in the first place. Therefore, no matter how much the

French teacher appeals to the students, they do not acknowledge that the sky contains other colors. According to Farsi and Hallaji (2022), the importance of the scene in the French class “lies in its power to show how deep the categorizing and positioning forces of society have penetrated into individuals’ cognitive lives” (p. 55). The efforts of the French teacher to break in-betweenness seem futile, as are the real milkman and issue women, with no fundamental change being achieved. But even if these acts of defiance do not directly have an obvious impact on society, it is precious to have pioneers in the community who have dared to break in-betweenness. They dare to cross the boundaries of in-betweenness and try to stop the ravages of in-betweenness on people’s minds. This is a ray of vibrant life in the gloomy *Milkman*.

An Analysis of Liminality and Permanent Liminality in *Milkman*

It is a pity that even with localized breaks, people in the Northern Ireland never quit in-betweenness and move out of the state of liminality. Rather, they step into permanent liminality. In this section, this paper will reveal how middle sister and Northern Ireland society possess permanent liminality. By identifying Northern Ireland as a liminal region, this paper will specifically analyze how liminality is at the core of Northern Irish society, leading to the performances of various in-between behaviors.

The Tragedy of Middle Sister and Northern Ireland: They Step into Permanent Liminality

In *Milkman*, Milkman is not able to keep harassing middle sister. One day, he dies. Nevertheless, even after Milkman’s death, middle sister’s life could not go back to the past due to a series of effects brought about by his harassment. The perception of middle sister in the minds of the community members has been completely changed, which could not be restored with the disappearance of Milkman. The shadow of Milkman will always haunt middle sister, as Burns (2018) wrote:

The death of Milkman wouldn’t mean, for me, the end of Milkman. Because of their stories; because they thought Milkman had gained ownership; because of my haughtiness...because of all these because, perhaps it suited the more extreme in the area to push the rumour out completely and have it be me and not that state death squad who’d orchestrated the killing of Milkman all along. (p. 256)

Thus, middle sister will remain in a permanent liminality, unable to escape the pain that Milkman exerts. However, except for the extra liminality given by Milkman, middle sister’s life itself is always in a permanent liminality because liminality is the key to living in political turmoil. As long as the chaos does not end, people’s lives will not come out of liminality.

After the Troubles, the signing of Good Friday Agreement in 1998 was an important milestone in the peace process in Northern Ireland, marking a temporary stabilization and a new phase in the society. However, having the presence of the agreement, could Northern Irish people really be able to step out of liminality? The answer is no. Mac Ginty et al. (2007) stated that, since the signing of GFA, “the level of violence in Northern Ireland has reduced but many problematic issues related to governance, sectarianism, and community relations remain on the political agenda and have destabilized the post-peace accord environment” (p. 1). Nagle (2017) concluded that “the augurs for the future of the GFA are not good” (p. 412). Tonge and Gomez (2015) also purposed that “despite political progress in Northern Ireland, the polity may arguably only fully stabilise when its population regards themselves as ‘Northern Irish’ rather than merely as subsets of British and Irish parent nations” (p. 276). It can be seen that GFA only brings about a military ceasefire, but fails to address the identity, governance and religious issues in Northern Ireland. For the nearly two decades after the GFA, Bartnik (2021) summarized that the “transition have not been too effective in rooting out sectarian mentality” (p. 69).^{ix} Additionally, Brexit has even made the issue of Northern Ireland more complicated. O’Brennan (2023) pointed out that after 2016, Northern Ireland has become “the main zone of contention between the EU and UK” (p. 133). O’Brennan (2023) used the theory of liminality to explore the “in-between” experience of Northern Ireland since it is involved in Brexit and demonstrated that “being ‘in between’ no longer means transitioning from one condition to another. It can mean being permanently stuck between different

constitutional landscapes with a knock-on impact on identities and territorial relationships” (p. 148). Fitting the context of Brexit was also one of the key reasons *Milkman* has won the Booker Prize. Therefore, it can be observed that even after the Troubles, Northern Ireland, because of the complexity of its political and territorial issues, has always possessed a liminality.

Thus, just as middle sister has lived with a permanent liminality, the whole society of Northern Ireland has always been in a permanent liminality, too. According to Bartnik (2021), based on the current state in Northern Ireland, Burns orients herself amongst the community of authors who feel worrying, rather than amongst those who serve to pacify. Burns’s narrative is fraught with the potential for confrontation or painful fissures, insisting on a return to the roots of Northern Ireland’s divisions. The traumas of the past seem to be covered up, but as soon as an event stimulates them, such as Brexit, the conflict and hatred in Northern Ireland are galvanized (p. 65). Thus, through *Milkman*, Burns not only portrays the tensions and conflicts of the Troubles in the 1970s, but also reveals that today’s Northern Ireland has not come out of liminality either, demonstrating her unease with the present Northern Ireland.

Liminality is the Core: Liminality is the Condition and In-betweenness is the Representation

Based on the analysis of in-betweenness and permanent liminality above, the paper finds that the state of social chaos and disorder in Northern Ireland during the 1970s is the root cause of the adoption of in-betweenness and liminality by the residents of Ardoyne community. Lamb (2010) defined that “liminality is a category of experience in which social actors are on the thresholds of change prompted by uncertainty and instability” (p. 1007), and Murphy (2024) presented that “liminal processes are not necessarily pleasant and may present difficulties, stressful environments and significant self-doubt” (p. 3). Regarding the Troubles, Murphy (2024) also wrote that “during this time, violence in the form of assassinations, bombs, rioting, police, army and paramilitary brutality was a daily reality and all activities occur in that shadow” (p. 7). This is the exact background that runs through *Milkman*, with the expressions such as “petrol bombs,” “carbombs” and “riots” appearing countless times in the novel. O’ Brennan (2023) pointed out that “liminal territory is identified as an uncomfortable place to live in, as precarious and potentially violent. These are physical spaces that frequently exhibit contradiction, contestation, hybridity, social exclusion and vulnerabilities (individual and collective)” (p. 136). Therefore, this paper holds the idea that Northern Ireland in the 1970s was a liminal space abound with liminality. Out of uncertainty about the identity and politics, Northern Ireland can be seen as a liminal territory, where liminality is the prerequisite for living. This is the scene depicted in *Milkman*: “The imperative not to cross any border that is not socially accepted eventually leads to the denial of personal freedom” (Haekel, 2023, p. 74). In addition, *Milkman* also presents what Murphy and McDowell (2019) asserted: “Liminality can be a collective as well as an individual experience” (p. 2502). Apart from middle sister, the majority of the residents in Ardoyne community insist on their adherence to liminality, without the opportunities to be the real themselves.

Therefore, inspired by O’ Brennan (2023): “Liminality as a condition of ‘in-betweenness’” (p. 135), this paper argues that liminality is the largest category, with permanent liminality and in-betweenness contained underneath. It is precisely because Northern Ireland in the 1970s was a liminal territory that it possessed the kernel of liminality, which led to the emergence and representation of in-betweenness and permanent liminality. However, whether it is liminality, permanent liminality or in-betweenness, the oppression brought to the people in Northern Ireland, especially middle sister, is endless. Under the scope of politics and gender, “the narrator’s own experiences of sexual harassment offer a further exposé of the collusion of nationalism and patriarchy in the repression of women” (Éigeartaigh, 2020, p. 48). Nevertheless, the place that exists oppression and injustice must also exist resistance and revolt. The previous section has already shown some examples of characters trying to break in-betweenness, and in the next section on *communitas*, readers will further see resistance from middle sister and other roles, especially middle sister’s feminist agency and how the women in the community unite to generate feminist power against injustice.

The Smallest Portion but the Largest Power: The “Communitas” in *Milkman* and the Relationship Model

In this section, the paper will address the communitas, which is the precious fellowship, and most importantly, the salvation in *Milkman*. According to Downes (2021), “redemption remains the nuclear hope in *Milkman*” (p. 237). From the characters like third brother-in-law, longest friend, ma, and even all the other women in the community, communitas can be seen and an enormous unity force is manifested.

In the course of liminality, middle sister and third brother-in-law form what Turner defined “communitas.” Third brother-in-law is a reliable person for middle sister. He is physically strong and does not go overly concerned with the outside world. He can give middle sister a sense of security, which is the reason why she goes running with him after being harassed by Milkman. Third brother-in-law also conveys a lot of support to middle sister whenever she feels vulnerable. When the community is flooded with rumors, third brother-in-law does not choose to believe it, but expresses console: “I must say, sister-in-law, I wouldn’t have expected you to be perpetuating gossip, never mind telegraphing it through such a wide ranging but distorting medium as that” (Burns, 2018, p. 57). This is the extremely precious trust and comfort that even the mother and sisters of middle sister do not give. After McSomebody tries to hurt middle sister, which she is indifferent with, third brother-in-law is serious: “‘Pointful to me, sister-in-law,’ said brother-in-law. ‘And what of principles? You’re a woman... You’re my sister-in-law... he’s a bastard and would’ve been a bastard even if they hadn’t got murdered’” (Burns, 2018, pp. 288-289). Third brother-in-law fully shows concern for middle sister and rage at McSomebody for bullying the lady. For middle sister, “brother-in-law was now seriously cross and I was touched by his crossness” (Burns, 2018, p. 289). Third brother-in-law’s caring, comfort and righteousness can be seen as a light in middle sister’s dark life. Furthermore, at the end of the novel, middle sister’s life is getting better and she continues to run with third brother-in-law: “Landing on the pavement in the direction of the parks & reservoirs, I exhaled this light and for a moment, just a moment, I almost nearly laughed” (Burns, 2018, p. 290). By ending on a positive note, readers also enable to see that “Burns’ intensely felt redemptive ethos so trumps even her grief, anger and peerless satirical bite” (Downes, 2021, p. 239). The respect for women shown by third brother-in-law, and the communitas they form is vital for middle sister to survive the trouble and is a powerful weapon against the irrational society.

Apart from third brother-in-law, middle sister and her longest friend also exist communitas. During a meeting, middle sister confides in longest friend about everything she has experienced. Longest friend just listens quietly, which makes middle sister feel very comfortable because finally, someone is listening to her. “I had told out to the right person... I was heard, and it felt good and respectful to be heard, to be got, not to be interrupted or cut off by opinionated, poorly attuned people” (Burns, 2018, pp. 168-169). Subsequently, as a sincere friend, longest friend points out all of middle sister’s behaviors that are strange for the community and gives middle sister the most heartfelt advice from the perspective of a rule-abiding person. In this conversation, middle sister not only releases herself, but also gains honest opinions.

Additionally, middle sister displays her strongest expression of defiance in *Milkman* during the communication with her trusted friend:

Just because I’m outnumbered in my reading-while-walking,’ I said, ‘doesn’t mean I’m wrong. What if one person happened to be sane, longest friend, against a whole background, a race mind, that wasn’t sane, that person would probably be viewed by the mass consciousness as mad—but would that person be mad?’ (Burns, 2018, p. 171)

The question middle sister proposes demonstrates her defiant spirit. In this crazy and violent society, she keeps her head and does not go with the flow (choosing liminality) like everyone else. Even when she finally has to compromise, which is represented by giving up reading-while-walking, she claims that it is the only thing she can waive. She rejects pandering to the social norms persistently: “I needed my silence, my unaccommodation, to shield me from pawing and from molestation by questions... This was my one bit of power in this disempowering world” (Burns, 2018, p. 174). Thus, it can be seen that when confronted by her longtime friend, middle sister speaks her true mind. Longest friend is also willing to

take in all of her thoughts and gives precious suggestions according to the reality. This *communitas* between friends allows middle sister to release her repressed inner self to a certain extent, and manifests her dissatisfaction and rebellion against the patriarchal society. According to Alder (2024), the repression from patriarchy, which is “the danger of an older man talking uninvitedly to a much younger woman and trying to establish himself within her personal boundaries...is simultaneously exacerbated and hidden by those ‘higher’ political and communal structures of violence” (p. 136). From here, the threefold violence inflicted on middle sister is clearly on display: The political chaos of Northern Ireland; the hostility of the community’s rumors and virulent assessment; and the patriarchal violence of Milkman and “this bellicose world” (Alder, 2024, p. 140), where “female subjectivity is purely associative, inherently based on their male counterparts” (Alder, 2024, p. 140). Deiana (2022) also pointed out how the “recurrent, yet unspeakable, experience of gendered violence in the story becomes entangled with the complex matrix of the Troubles as felt and embodied by Middle Sister and the wider community that inhabit the unnamed conflict city” (p. 36). However, faced with the interweaving of multiple violence, middle sister fully demonstrates her feminist power both in language and action. As Zeeshan et al. (2024) observed: Middle sister “could have been a big feminist, but the power of the Milkman and societal filth makes her just another woman who is trying to be free of that hegemonic shadow” (p. 62). Both the *communitas* middle sister has formed above and the breaking of liminality exemplify her feminist agency.

In addition, two sets of *communitas* emerge after the real milkman was shot as an anti-government person. One is that the women in the community unite and form *communitas* to demand the government release the real milkman alive. “Matters had moved on too, it seemed, throughout the whole of the area regarding real milkman” (Burns, 2018, p. 266). The women pray for the real milkman and also exert pressure on the government, which reflects women’s dissatisfaction with unjustified military and political oppression and their feminist power in resistance. The second group of *communitas* is middle sister and ma. Although the two hold completely different positions and ideas, which has been analyzed above, middle sister eventually chooses to understand ma. Ma changes a lot after the injury of the real milkman and starts to face her feelings for him squarely. Ma begins to care about her appearance and often goes to middle sister’s room to find clothes and shoes to dress up, like a girl in love. However, ma is still not confident enough and her nervousness is obvious. Though middle sister hates it when ma enters her room and touches her things, she senses ma’s insecurity and decides to support and understand her, which further reflects the warmth between women. “Because of her panic though, and because she seemed now to have entered some vulnerable, regressed, strange transition period, I found myself handing her a pair of low slingbacks and saying, ‘Try these on, ma’ instead” (Burns, 2018, p. 265). The fact that ma finally breaks the in-betweenness of love, and chooses a representative “beyond-the-pale” person, namely the real milkman, as her lover, is a huge turnaround. Middle sister may be very delighted with this transformation.

Last, there is *communitas* between ma and other women in the community, which demonstrates feminist power once more. When middle sister is poisoned by tablets girl, ma shoulders the responsibility of caring. Ma does not send middle sister to the hospital because “the hospital is one of many contentious zones associated with informership and the state, and anyone who attends is the subject of gossip, suspicion, and perhaps punishment” (Wall, 2023, p. 73). Therefore, other women in the community come to help during this difficult time for both ma and middle sister: “So also appeared neighbours, bearing demijohns, bell-jars...They had materialised out of nowhere which was usual with neighbours on occasions of ‘not going to hospital’. Like ma, they were prepared, with nightdress sleeves rolled up” (Burns, 2018, pp. 190-191). Wall (2023) commented that “this insistence on ‘not going to hospital’ also illustrates women’s role in the retention of the community ‘purity’ and safety” (p. 73). *Milkman* demonstrates that once there is a situation involving healing, the women in the community, including ma, are there to help, which exemplifies the mutual help of people in a state of liminality. The *communitas* formed by women in the community at the time of the real milkman’s injury and middle sister’s intoxication both present the power of women, as explained by Zeeshan et al. (2024): “The transformative potential of collective female solidarity is formidable. By illustrating how women unite and support each other, the story reveals the profound strength and influence that emerge when they

join forces against systemic oppression” (p. 64). The feminine power, friendship power and family affection shown by the *communitas* above all illustrate what Coons (2024) concluded: “Middle sister’s retroactive narrativizing of her encounters with this tumultuous history refutes militaristic patriarchy’s totalizing trauma, its commandments of silence and obedience, and ushers forth different, if imperfect, notions of collectivity, care, and political belonging” (p. 215). The force of resistance gives readers a respite in *Milkman*’s depressing world, and also offers schemes for the characters to break liminality.

To conclude, this paper analyzes *Milkman* from “in-betweenness,” “permanent liminality,” and “communitas.” Doshi (2022) illustrated that “liminality presents sites of fear, confusion, void, inversion, on the one hand, and hope, potentiality, opportunities, transformation, on the other hand” (p. 1134). This is exactly what *Milkman* exemplifies. On the one side, *Milkman* shows readers the chaos of Northern Ireland in a state of liminality, which leads to the common masses having liminality and presenting a series of in-between behaviors. Besides, what is more lamentable is that even after the Troubles in the 1970s, Northern Ireland is still not able to come out of the liminal state. Nevertheless, on the other side, the liminality of Northern Ireland in *Milkman* also gives readers a glimpse of the resistance of the underclass. By breaking in-betweenness and forming *communitas*, how people help each other in the midst of the Troubles can be seen, adding hope for change to a dark society. Therefore, based on the overall analysis for liminality, the keywords in this paper can produce the following relationship model:

Figure 1. The Relationship Model among “Liminality,” “Permanent Liminality,” “In-betweenness” and “Communitas”

In this model, liminality is the biggest part and covers the three keywords in this paper. Since Northern Ireland is a liminal region, the masses living in Northern Ireland must have a liminal nature. Unfortunately, neither middle sister nor Northern Ireland can move out of liminality and therefore into permanent liminality. Under these two, since liminality, as the kernel of society, is the condition of in-betweenness, many behaviors of in-betweenness are generated. However, under the weight of liminality, permanent liminality and in-betweenness, *communitas* carries all as the mainstay. Although *communitas* in the subalterns may not be powerful enough to bring fundamental transformation to the society, it is necessary for people to live in an unorganized society. Even if it is the smallest part of the model, it is the strongest power to stimulate resistance and rebellion. With the support of *communitas*, *Milkman* conveys positivity by ending with middle sister almost laughing. Even though Northern Ireland is under an enormous shadow of liminality, the presence of *communitas* gives a sense of human warmth, thus generating significant physical and spiritual comfort.

Conclusion

To summarize, in the field of liminality, this paper begins by employing Spivak's postcolonial theory of "in-betweenness" to demonstrate the in-between state of the characters in *Milkman*, which in turn reveals the personal complexity and heterogeneity of the subalterns. Next, the paper applies Szakolczai's concept of "permanent liminality" to explore that middle sister is in the midst of permanent liminality, revealing that the broader context of the whole fiction is permanent liminality, because as long as Northern Ireland does not gain stability, people's state of liminality will not end. This paper therefore further analyzes how Northern Ireland, after the signing of the GFA, remains in a state of liminality until today. This paper utilizes the opinion proposed by O'Brennan (2023) regarding the analysis of the British-EU contestation over Northern Ireland: "Liminality as a condition of 'in-betweenness'" (p. 135), and argues that it is equally applicable to Northern Ireland at the time of the Troubles in the 1970s. Northern Ireland is a liminal territory, and its political instability has made the possession of liminality the key to survive. Liminality is the essence, the condition, which leads to numerous manifestations of in-betweenness, as the specified textual analysis of *Milkman* shown above.

Then the paper is followed by Victor Turner's theory of liminality, adopting the keyword "communitas," to analyze the "communitas" established in *Milkman* and how "communitas" represents hopefully resistant forces. The paper presents a relationship model in which liminality is the largest part, then permanent liminality, and then followed by in-betweenness, and finally communitas, which is the smallest part yet the most important part. This paper illustrates how communitas contains tremendous resistant power within a small portion.

Noble and Walker (1997) illustrated that liminality can "significantly disrupt one's internal sense of self or place within a social system" (pp. 31-32). Johnsen and Sørensen (2015) also explained that "being in liminality therefore involves a fundamental transformation of one's social conditions as well as the existential circumstances of one's life" (p. 323). Indeed, as a result of Milkman's sexual harassment, the liminal experience in *Milkman* demonstrates middle sister's shifting identity in Ardoyne community, from a girl who behaves strangely to the mistress of a high-ranking member of a military organization. The rumors in the community and the changing attitudes of the people around middle sister also make her perception of her own identity increasingly blurred. Furthermore, the chaotic and disorganized society poses many challenges for everyone in Northern Ireland. However, the resulting liminal story is not just about people being forced to choose liminality; it also shows how people use liminality to form communitas to resist. Characters like middle sister, the real milkman, ma, third brother-in-law, French teacher, issue women, and all the women in the community all challenge their submissive identity they are supposed to have and strive to break the established liminality in order to bring about some changes. Danacı (2020) mentioned that "as the middle sister survives the nightmare she was subjected to, her story and eventual recovery offer a similar confrontation and a process of healing for the country itself" (p. 304). The promising ending of middle sister may hint at Burns's expectations for Northern Ireland. Moreover, the story of *Milkman* is real and such horrible situations depicted in the novel can happen to any area and to any person, just as Morales-Ladrón (2023) stated: Ardoyne community "mirrors any totalitarian society ruled by silence and fear" (p. 274). By analyzing in-betweenness and liminality of Northern Ireland in the 1970s, this paper not only wishes to offer a historical reference to the present Northern Irish society, but also hopes to shed some light on the countries and people that are in liminal state across the globe.

Conflict of interests

No conflict of interest.

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ⁱ Callan (2023) analyzed the innovation of *Milkman* compared with classical dystopian novels like *Brave New World* and *Nineteen Eighty-Four*, exploring the dystopian elements in *Milkman* and how to recover from dystopia. Callan thought that *Milkman* generated reconsideration for “both the conflict in Northern Ireland and the dystopian genre” (p. 513) and further pointed out that *Milkman* is not just identifying readers with characters who courageously reject dystopia, but encourages readers to acknowledge that we may be the ones who enhance dystopia, no matter we plan to or not (Callan, 2023, p. 523).

ⁱⁱ Morales-Ladrón (2023) applied Michel Foucault's theory of panopticon and biopower to examine the euphemisms and groupthink in *Milkman*, pointing out that “in the postpanopticon society of *Milkman*, silence is the result of a self-imposed discipline of control nurtured by a disempowered microstructure that facilitates the success of such same technology of power (p. 10).

ⁱⁱⁱ Based on solid evidence in *Milkman*, such as analyzing soldiers and men in the community, Darling (2021) presented that “naming connotes a sense of gendered threat and violence” (p. 316). Linguistic resistance is limited and “middle sister becomes an object to be known epistemologically” (Darling, 2021, p. 318).

^{iv} By utilizing Michel de Certeau's theory of tactic and Maria Tumarkin's theory of traumascapes, Mathuria (2022) stated that “walking is a tactic that allows for opportunities of subversion” (p. 187) as well as identified that “the ten-minute area is a ‘traumascape’” (Mathuria, 2022, p. 192).

^v Malone (2022) contradicted what Hutton (2019) studied that “*Milkman* is a Bildungsroman which focuses, in the end, on how middle sister resolves her difficulties and develops” (Hutton, 2019, p. 366). Instead, Malone (2022) thought that *Milkman* is a picaresque, insisting “Burns' use and détournement of the picaresque works to create a protective distance between the narrator and the events she recalls” (p. 1145).

^{vi} The author summarized the main content of Routray and Gaur's paper, which explores how the first-person narrative technique in *Milkman* reveals gender and social conflict through the lens of female phenomenology. Routray and Gaur (2024) concluded that “through a narrative technique that elegantly weaves personal accounts into the fabric of collective struggles, Anna Burns's first-person portrayal of the middle sister constitutes a testament of the resilience of the human spirit and personal fortitude...” (p. 8).

vii Hossain (2023) analyzed middle sister's resistance through feminist poststructuralism, discussing how she "executes her vengeance and retaliation to the orthodox gender-perpetrating practices of her community both during the violent time and the normal one" and how "she utilizes her language to evade the typical elements antagonistic to the women folk, and thereby, vibrantly establishes her selfhood deputy to her kind in totality" (p. 207).

viii Maqbool et al. (2022) set out from Marxist feminism: What *Milkman* portrays is that economic injustice results from women's limited opportunities to "earn and own their sources of production" (p. 1026).

ix Bartnik (2021) summarized the content of Declan Long's book *Ghost-Haunted Land: Contemporary Art and Post-Troubles Northern Ireland*. In this book, Long (2017) emphasized the social division in Northern Ireland, pointing out that "the most disturbing indications of this stubbornly unyielding social division are found in the many 'interface areas' of towns and cities in Northern Ireland" (p. 38).

